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DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

OPTION LAND SURVEYING

Evaluation of land use and land and cover change 2000-2010-2020.

Case study: Nyabugogo wetland”

*A project report submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of an
Advanced Diploma in civil Engineering,
Land surveying Option*

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DECLARATION

We, **Philbert DUSHIMIRIMANA** and **Marie Isabelle DUSHIME** declare that the content of this dissertation is our own work except where acknowledged. It has never been presented or submitted anywhere else for any other or similar award at any other university or institution of high learning for the award of any a degree.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to:

- ❖ Almighty God
- ❖ My father and Mother
- ❖ Brothers and Sisters for their inspirations
- ❖ IPRC NGOMA Staffs and Lectures

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, we would like to thank the Almighty God who provided the required knowledge and good health during our studies. Thank you, Lord, we owe you a great debt. This study could not have been successful if it was not for the assistance, contributions and cooperation we got from very important people. We express our sincere gratitude to our supervisor, **Marie Grace MUTIMUCYEYE**. For her guidance and constructive criticism helped us to properly shape this research work. From the beginning, we had mixed ideas where we cannot even shape what we were thinking is real life problem we wanted to sort out. Therefore, we express our gratitude to our supervisor who understand the path we wanted to take our project in and shape it much better. Without her continuous constructive criticism and support, this project could not have been successful, we thank her so much. We also extend our appreciation to all lecturers in Program of Land survey at IPRC Ngoma without them, we could not have carried out a work of this kind. By considering the starting point of this project, we are very sure that all lecturers who taught us contribute to this project in one way or another.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION AND ACCRONYMS

Geographical Information System

GIS, 1

Integrated Polytechnic Regional Collage

IPRC, 2

land use land cover

LULC, 3

National Institute of Statistic Rwanda

NISR, 4

LS, 5

Landscape services

ES, 6

Ecosystem services

ABSATRACT

Humankind to fulfill its needs has put natural resources of the Earth to a severe pressure. The rate of degradation and depletion of earth resources has accelerated tremendously in view of the over increasing demographic pressure. Therefore, this study aims to map landscape cover of Nyabugogo wetland in order to know how much area is suitable for wildlife species, area for cultivation and what areas are affected due to anthropogenic pressure. However, in this study, Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques will be used. Remotely sensed data procured from satellite image from 2000-2010-2020 and collateral data generated from topographic maps was be processed using ERDAS IMAGINE and ArcGIS software's. Then, in result landscape cover map of the study area was prepared from satellite data using supervised maximum likelihood classification technique, where we have seen that wetland zone changes to building up area is 5.74%, agriculture to forest is 24.68%, forest to wetland 5.67%, vegetation to vegetation 22.41% and agriculture to building is 41.5%. Moreover, the result help to better understand landscape cover change in Nyabugogo wetland and guide RDB decision makers to ensure proper management of the national wetland.

Keywords:

1. Wetland
2. Land
3. Land use
4. Land cover

CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

I.1. General Introduction

Land use and land cover (LULC) is a term that refers to both land use categories and different types of land cover. The material that physically shelters the terrestrial surface is referred to as the land cover. Human activities on the land are known as land use, and it typically but not always has something to do with land cover. Changes in land use and land cover are a vital part of current sustainable land conservation and environmental change supervising strategies. Changes in LULC are pervasive, quickening, and taking place at the local, regional, and global levels. LULC dynamics are a pervasive, quickening, and important process that is primarily fueled by human activity and results in modifications that have an impact on people's quality of life.

The LULC dynamics affect the availability of many crucial resources, including water, soil, and vegetation. These modifications have adverse effects. Rwanda's natural resources are impacted by a number of interconnected problems, including population increase, agricultural expansion, resettlement, rapid urbanization, extreme weather, and environmental degradation [1]

The evaluation of land use/cover change in Nyabugogo wetland focuses on understanding the historical and current changes in land use and vegetation cover within the wetland boundaries. This assessment helps in monitoring and managing the wetland 's ecosystems, identifying potential threats and challenges, and formulating conservation strategies.

Therefore, remote sensing data procured from satellite Landsat and collateral data generated from topographic maps will be processed by using ERDAS IMAGINE and Arc GIS. Land-use land-cover map of the study area will be prepared from satellite data using supervised maximum likelihood classification technique, which was revealed that Wetland supports diversified.

Land is defined as a place on which all human activity is being conducted. Use of land resources by the people gives rise to land use" which varies with the purposes it serves, whether they be food production, provision of shelter, recreation, extraction and processing of materials, and the bio-physical characteristics of land itself. Hence, land use is being shaped under the influence of two broad sets of forces – human needs and environmental features and processes. The terms land use and land cover are not synonymous and the literature draws attention to their use and land cover

change. Land cover is the biophysical state of the earth's surface differences so that they are used properly in studies of land and immediate subsurface [2][3].

Land cover deals with the quantity and type of surface vegetation, water, and earth materials. i.e., man-made constructions (buildings etc.), the type of material used in housing structure. The term land cover originally referred to the type of vegetation that covered the land surface, but has broadened subsequently to include other aspects of the physical environment also, such as soils, biodiversity and surfaces and groundwater[4].

I.2. Background of the study

Nyabugogo natural wetland covers 220 ha and is located within the Kigali City, Rwanda's capital. Nyabugogo wetland is located between 1,354 m to 2,278 m above sea level and between 1°94'S and 30°04'E. It drains an area of 1,647 km² within the Nyabugogo catchment and it covers both rural and urban areas, including Kigali [5]

Nyabugogo wetland cuts across two districts Nyarugenge and Gasabo with an estimated population of 825,767 inhabitants. The wetland is part of the Nyabugogo catchment which cuts across Eastern Province (Kayonza, Rwamagana, and Gatsibo districts), and Northern Province Gicumbi and Rulindo and other districts of Kigali city such as Kicukiro, Nyarugenge, and Gasabo districts where the current study area is located. Its estimated population is about 1,135,428 inhabitants [6]

Nyabugogo catchment is a level 2 catchment within the Nile basin and a tributary of the lower Nyabarongo River. It is rather centrally located with a section extending into the eastern and dryer part of the country. The catchment covers significant parts of the districts of Rulindo, Gicumbi, Gatsibo, Kayonza, Rwamagana, Gasabo, Kicukiro, and Nyarugenge. It has a total surface area of 1,661 km², representing 6.31 % of the total surface area of Rwanda (26,338 km²). Lake Muhazi, which is about 80 km long and runs east-west, is a central feature of the catchment. The Nyabugogo River is 45.97 km long, measured from the outflow of Lake Muhazi to its confluence with the lower Nyabarongo River near Kigali at an altitude of about 1,360 masl. The highest point of the catchment is at 2,280 masl in the northern part of the catchment. The main tributaries of the Nyabugogo River are rivers Mwange, Muzanza, Rusine, Kajevuba and Yanze. The dry season runs from late May to early September, with the rainy period in October to early December, a

slight dip around the month of January, and a peak rainy season during March and April, up to early May. Dry season months are prolonged in lower altitude areas and towards the east. [7]

I.3. Problem Statement

Humankind to fulfil its needs has put natural resources of the earth to a severe pressure. The rate of degradation and depletion of earth resources has accelerated tremendously in view of the over increasing demographic pressure. Nyabugogo Wetland in Rwanda faces pressing challenges related to its land use and land cover, necessitating a comprehensive evaluation. This vital ecosystem, situated in the heart of Kigali, is encountering significant alterations in its landscape, which raise concerns about its ecological integrity and long-term sustainability. The evaluation of land use and land cover of Nyabugogo wetlands is essential to assess the current state and changes occurring in these critical ecosystems. Wetlands play a vital role in maintaining biodiversity, water quality, and ecological balance, but they are increasingly threatened by urbanization, agriculture, and climate change. This project intends to map landscape cover to see the changes of Nyabugogo wetland from 2000-2010-2020 using Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographical Information System (GIS) in order to know Nyabugogo wetland landscape cover changes over stated period and how to monitor these changes.

1.4. Objectives

The main objective of this study is to evaluate land use land cover change of Nyabugogo wetland from 2000-2010-2020 using Remote sensing and GIS.

1.4.1. Specific objective

1. Characterize Land Use and Land Cover Changes Over a Specific Period of Time.
2. Change Detection and Trend Analysis.
3. Land Management Recommendation

1.5. Methodology

Remote sensing techniques used to collect information. These information's were helped to complete attribute table. Spatial data was be recorded using DGPS. All data, attribute data and spatial data will be treated and analyzed in ArcGIS to give good and perfect result, there is some tools which was used mostly like erase, editor and clip.

1.6. Organization of The Study

This study is organized in following five chapters:

1. The first one deal with the background information to the study, the definition of the research problem, objectives and their corresponding research questions, interest of the topic, scope and limitation of the study.
2. In the second chapter some definitions and literature review related to the evaluation of land use and land cover were discussed.
3. Chapter three explain the methodology used to conduct this research where source of data used, equipment used in collection of data, description of the study area of this research are shown and discussed.
4. Chapter four shown the analysis and interpretation of the results.
5. Finally, Chapter five, which closes the report, provides a summary to the content in the report and gives recommendations and conclusion for future works.

1.7. SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF RESEARCH

This study was attentive on evaluation of land use and land cover of Nyabugogo wetland and processing data in ArcGIS for determining changes over period of time. This topic is selection for those more related to land use and land cover. there is no other information encountered so far, the study case.

1.8. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

1.8.1. PERSONAL SIGNIFICANCE

It helped to increase our knowledge and skills, learn the best technics, methods, and procedures in our daily career as land surveyor. And it increased our knowledge and Evaluation of land use and land and cover change.

1.8.2. INSTITUTION SIGNIFICANCE

The results of this **Evaluation of land use and land and land cover change** will be reference to other students of IRP NGOMA. It will create a good picture of RP NGOMA as the example of quality education, and ALSO will promote RP NGOMA to make it famous in that field of land surveying.

1.8.3. Government Signification

Achievement on implementation of this project will provide the job to the surrounding people of project. Once this project is achieved the people will use in solving the problem related mis-use of land use.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Definitions of Technical Terms

1. Wetland: is a low-lying area that is saturated with water, either permanently or seasonally, and contains hydric soils and aquatic vegetation.[8]

2. Land use: refers to the way in which a piece of land is utilized or developed by humans for various purposes. It encompasses the activities, structures, or functions that take place on a particular area of land. Land use can vary significantly and may include a wide range of purposes and activities, such as residential, agriculture, recreational, industrial.[9]. Where [10] explain why "land use" and "land cover" are not identical terms. Land cover denotes the physical, chemical, or biological categorization of the terrestrial surface, for example, grassland, forest, or concrete, whereas land use refers to purposes associated with that cover-raising cattle, recreation, or urban living.

3. Land cover: Land cover refers to the physical characteristics of the Earth's surface, including the natural and human-made features that cover the land. It encompasses a wide range of categories and types, which are typically classified based on the dominant materials or uses found in a particular area. Land cover is an important concept in fields such as geography, environmental science, urban planning, and land use management. Forests: Areas dominated by trees and woody vegetation. Including Grasslands, Wetlands, Agricultural Land, Urban Areas, Water Bodies.[11]. Where [12] define land cover "as the biophysical state of Earth's surface and immediate subsurface." The term refers to the type of vegetation that covers the land surface, other aspects of the physical environment, such as soils, biodiversity, surfaces, and groundwater, as well as to human structures, such as buildings or pavement.

2.2. Definitions and Concept of land

2.2.1. Land is the surface of the earth identified by specific boundaries, including the airspace above that portion of surface, the minerals beneath it, and surrounding biodiversity and development on that surface. Land is the surface of the earth, the materials beneath it, the air above

and all things fixed to the soil. Land is a unique asset because it is immovable; its value depends on its location; and with growing population its demand keeps increasing.

2.2.2. Land as a Natural Asset

Land can include anything that's on the ground, which means that buildings, trees, and water are a part of land as an asset. The term land encompasses all physical elements, bestowed by nature, to a specific area or piece of property the environment, fields, forests, minerals, climate, animals, and bodies or sources of water. A landowner may be entitled to a wealth of natural resources on their property including plants, human and animal life, soil, minerals, geographical location, electromagnetic features, and geophysical occurrences. Because natural gas and oil in the United States are being depleted, the land that contains these resources is of great value. In many cases, drilling and oil companies pay landowners substantial sums of money for the right to use their land to access such natural resources, particularly if the land is rich in a specific resource [13]

2.3. Landscape

2.3.1. Introduction to landscape

A **landscape** is the visible features of an area of land, its landforms, and how they integrate with natural or man-made features. A landscape includes the physical elements of geophysical defined landforms such as (ice-capped) mountains, hills, water bodies such as rivers, lakes, ponds and the sea, living elements of land cover including indigenous vegetation, human elements including different forms of land use, buildings, and structures, and transitory elements such as lighting and weather conditions. Combining both their physical origins and the cultural overlay of human presence, often created over millennia, landscapes reflect a living synthesis of people and place that is vital to local and national identity [14].

The character of a landscape helps define the self-image of the people who inhabit it and a sense of place that differentiates one region from other regions. It is the dynamic backdrop to people's lives. Landscape can be as varied as farmland, a landscape park or wilderness.

The Earth has a vast range of landscapes, including the icy landscapes of polar regions, mountainous landscapes, vast arid desert landscapes, islands, and coastal landscapes,

densely forested or wooded landscapes including past boreal forests and tropical rainforests, and agricultural landscapes of temperate and tropical regions [15]

The activity of modifying the visible features of an area of land is referred to as landscaping. There are several definitions of what constitutes a landscape, depending on context. In common usage however, a landscape refers either to all the visible features of an area of land (usually rural), often considered in terms of aesthetic appeal, or to a pictorial representation of an area of countryside, specifically within the genre of landscape painting. When people deliberately improve the aesthetic appearance of a piece of land by changing contours and vegetation, etc.

It is said to have been landscaped, though the result may not constitute a landscape according to some definitions. In addition to the term and concept of ecosystem services (ES), which has become very popular over the past few years, a similar term has increasingly come into use: landscape services (LS). The word landscape is old and popular. It has many senses from territory to scenery. Geography uses this concept since Humboldt, which pointed out its spatiality and its physical and cultural characteristics[16].

The geographical approach of landscape concept emphasizes relationships between natural and cultural processes in a spatial portion. Depending on physical or cultural/symbolic approaches, one of both processes will prevail. In ecological approach, the main characteristics to define landscape are spatiality, heterogeneity and relationship between elements, including men or not. Here we propose a unified landscape concept defining it as a heterogeneous space portion where relationship between natural and cultural processes occur (Scheller, 2020).

2.3.2. The Landscape Concept Structure and Function

Regardless of how landscape is defined, the “concept” of a landscape is unequivocal. All landscapes have a user-defined structure (pattern) that is hypothesized to influence its function (process). This interaction between spatial pattern and process defines the landscape concept. Landscape structure. The structure of a landscape is defined by the particular spatial pattern being represented, and it consists of two components: composition and configuration. The composition of a landscape is defined by the spatial elements that are distinguished in the map and believed to be relevant to the landscape function under consideration [17].

Composition represents the non-spatial aspect of a landscape, since only number and abundance of landscape elements is considered, not their spatial configuration. The configuration of a

landscape is defined by the spatial character, arrangement and context of the elements. Configuration represents the spatial aspect of a landscape. Together these two components define the spatial pattern or heterogeneity of the landscape. Landscape function. The function of a landscape is defined by the phenomena under consideration and can be a multitude of different things. In general, the services that landscapes provide to humans are functions and include things like providing for biological diversity, recycling nutrients, sequestering carbon, producing clean water, etc.[18] .

2.4. Introduction to Land Use and Land Cover Change

Land cover deals with the quantity and type of surface vegetation, water, and earth materials. i.e., man-made constructions (buildings etc), the type of material used in housing structure. The term land cover originally referred to the type of vegetation that covered the land surface, but has broadened subsequently to include other aspects of the physical environment also, such as soils, biodiversity and surfaces and groundwater[19].

Land use and land cover (LULC) is a term that refers to both land use categories and different types of land cover. The material that physically shelters the terrestrial surface is referred to as the land cover. Human activities on the land are known as land use, and it typically but not always has something to do with land cover. Changes in land use and land cover are a vital part of current sustainable land conservation and environmental change supervising strategies. Changes in LULC are pervasive, quickening, and taking place at the local, regional, and global levels. LULC dynamics are a pervasive, quickening, and important process that is primarily fueled by human activity and results in modifications that have an impact on people's quality of life. The LULC dynamics affect the availability of many crucial resources, including water, soil, and vegetation. These modifications have adverse effects. Rwanda's natural resources are impacted by a number of interconnected problems, including population increase, agricultural expansion, resettlement, rapid urbanization, extreme weather, and environmental degradation.

2.5. Types of land use and land cover

2.5.1. Types of land uses are

- ✚ Residential Land Use - where people live (houses, apartment buildings)
- ✚ Institutional Land Use - government related (schools, town hall, police station)
- ✚ Recreational Land Use - for fun, entertainment purposes (parks)
- ✚ Open/ Vacant Space Land Use - empty land
- ✚ Commercial Land Use - places to do with [making] money (stores, banks)
- ✚ Industrial Land Use - working places that help industry (factories)
- ✚ Agricultural Land Use - land used to grow food etc. (farmland)
- ✚ Railway Land Use - railways
- ✚ Transportation Land Use -to do with transport (bus stops, roads)
- ✚ Government Land Use like "institutional"
- ✚ Utilities Land Use - like hydroelectricity towers

2.6.2. Types of land cover

Simply put, land cover is what covers the surface of the earth and land use describes how the land is used. Examples of land cover classes include:

- ✚ **Water**
- ✚ **Snow**
- ✚ **Grassland**
- ✚ **Forest**
- ✚ **bare soil [4]**

2.7. Importance of land use and land cover

1. **Environmental Conservation:** Proper land use and land cover management are essential for the conservation of natural habitats, biodiversity, and ecosystems. Maintaining right balance of forested areas, wetlands, and other natural landscapes helps preserve wildlife and ecological processes.

2. **Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation:** Land use and land cover changes significantly affect the Earth's climate. Forests, for instance, act as carbon sinks, absorbing greenhouse gases. Land use planning can help reduce emissions and increase resilience to climate change.
3. **Sustainable Agriculture:** Land use planning is vital for optimizing agricultural practices. It helps determine where crops should be grown, where livestock can graze.
4. **Urban Planning and Development:** Infrastructure: Land use decisions impact the development of cities and the location of essential infrastructure like roads, utilities, and public services. [20]

2.8. Land cover classification

Land use classifications are what you call the different desired or planned categories of future land uses on your comprehensive plan map or other document. Traditionally, the broad groupings are residential, commercial, and industrial. [21]

No.	Land cover class	Description
1	Forest	Woodland open general (15–65%) with herbaceous layer. Broadleaved deciduous trees, closed > (70–60) %. Vegetative cover is in balance with the abiotic and biotic forces of its biotope
2	Shrubland	Closed to open (thicket) (15–100%) scattered trees
3	Grassland	Herbaceous closed vegetation (15–100%) with some trees, shrub Savannah, and permanent marsh
4	Cultivated land	Areas where the natural vegetation has been removed or modified and replaced by other types of vegetative cover of anthropogenic origin. All vegetation that is planted or cultivated with intent to harvest is included in this class

No.	Land cover class	Description
5	Bare land	Bare rock and/or coarse fragments. Areas that do not have an artificial cover as a result of human activities. These areas include areas with less than 4% vegetative cover
6	Water bodies	This class refers to areas that are naturally covered by water, such as lakes, rivers, snow, or ice
7	Wetlands	Areas that are transitional between pure terrestrial and aquatic systems and where the water table is usually at or near the surface or the land is covered by shallow water
8	Artificial surfaces	Areas that have an artificial cover as a result of human activities, such as construction (cities, towns, and transportation), extraction (open mines and quarries), or waste disposal

Table 2.1: Classification of land cover

Negative impact of human activities to wetland

Human activities have had a significant impact on wetland use, leading to both positive and negative consequences. Some key impacts include:

- 1. Wetland Degradation:** Wetlands are often drained for agriculture, urban development, and infrastructure projects. This reduces their size and ecological function.
- 2. Water Pollution:** Runoff from industrial, agricultural, and urban areas can introduce pollutants like nutrients, heavy metals, and pesticides into wetlands. This can disrupt the delicate balance of wetland ecosystems.
- 3. Biodiversity Loss:** Habitat destruction and pollution lead to the decline of wetland species.
- 4. Climate Change:** Human activities also contribute to climate change, which affects wetlands through altered precipitation patterns, sea-level rise, and increased temperatures (reports, 2019,)

2.9. Introduction to GIS

A geographic information system is a conceptualized framework that provides the ability to capture and analyze spatial and geographic data, also a geographic information system [GIS] is a system that creates, manages, analyzes, and maps all types of data. GIS connect data to a map, integrating location data (where things are) with all types of descriptive information (where things are like there). This provides a foundation for mapping and analysis that is used in science and almost every industry. GIS helps users understand patterns, relationships, and

geographic context. The benefit includes improved communication and efficiency as well as better management and decision making [22].

2.9.1. Components of GIS

Similar to other information technologies, a GIS requires the following components besides geospatial data:

- 1. Hardware:** GIS hardware includes computers for data processing, data storage, and input/ output; printers and plotters for reports and hard-copy maps; digitizers and scanners for digitization of spatial data; and GPS and mobile devices for fieldwork (. Chang, 2012)
- 2. Software:** GIS software, either commercial or open source, includes programs and applications to be executed by a computer for data management, data analysis, data display, and other tasks.
- 3. People:** GIS professionals define the purpose and objectives for using GIS and interpret and present the results.
- 4. Methods:** A successful GIS operates according to a well-designed plan and business rules, which are the models and operating practices unique to each organization
- 5. Data** Possibly the most important component of a GIS is the data. Geographic data and related tabular data can be collected in-house or purchased from a commercial data provider. A GIS will integrate spatial data with other data resources and can even use a DBMS, used by most organizations to organize and maintain their data, to manage spatial data.

GIS-Data & Sources: The most important and expensive component of the Geographic Information System is Data which is generally known as fuel for GIS. Acquiring geographic data is an important factor in any geographic information system (GIS) effort. It has been estimated that data acquisition typically consumes 60 to 80 percent of the time and money spent on any given project.

Primary Data Capture: Primary data capture is a direct data acquisition methodology that is usually associated with some type of in-the-field effort. In the case of vector data,

directly captured data commonly comes from a global positioning system (GPS) or other types of surveying equipment such as a total station. Use of a total station allows field crews to quickly and accurately derive the topography for a particular landscape.

Secondary Data Capture: Secondary data capture is an indirect methodology that utilizes the vast amount of existing geospatial data available in both digital and hard-copy formats. GIS data is combination of graphic and tabular data. Documentation of GIS datasets is known as metadata contains such information as the coordinate system, when the data was created, when it was last updated, who created it and how to contact them and definitions for any of the code attribute data. Perhaps the most important component of a GIS is in the part of data used in GIS [23].

CHAPTER 3: MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter indicate the methods, tools and materials used to carry out the objectives of the study. The methodology used to get data from field. Which means the way followed in order to obtain the required information, the materials, equipment and tools which gathered and used to perform the objectives of research.

Materials and equipment

To extract and analyses the rate of landscape covers a combination of spectral reflectance and ground truth data contains particular spatial and attribute data was applied for maximum likelihood classifiers of Landsat dataset. This was done by appropriate software including Erdas imagine 2014 and ArcGIS 10.8 to process and analyses the data for the study.

1.2. Description of the study area

Nyabugogo wetland is located between 1,354 m to 2,278 m above sea level and between 1°94'S and 30°04'E. The wetland drains a total area of 1,647 km². Nyabugogo is located within the Nyabugogo catchment and it covers both rural and urban areas including the City of Kigali which is the capital city of Rwanda.

Nyabugogo wetland cuts across Two districts Nyarugenge and Gasabo with an estimated population of 825,767 inhabitants. The wetland is part of the Nyabugogo catchment which cuts across Eastern Province (Kayonza, Rwamagana, and Gatsibo districts), and Northern Province Gicumbi and Rulindo and other districts of Kigali city such as Kicukiro, Nyarugenge, and Gasabo districts where the current study area is located. Its estimated population is about 1,135,428 inhabitants [24].

Figure 3.1: Location of study area

1.3. Data collection

The Secondary data collection method has been obtained from various sources like Nyabugogo wetland maps, topographic maps, and satellite imageries. This type of data collection was used in this research. Satellite data that comprised of Three years multi - temporal satellite imageries (LANDSAT 8 imageries of 2000 - 2010 and 2020) acquired from the USGS GLOVIS website. In this study, Landsat images, GPS was used to record reference control points coordinates, ERDAS IMAGINE 2014 and GIS 10.8 software, Google earth images for further was used in the LULC classification.

The image data files have been downloaded in zipped files from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) website and extracted to Tiff format files. The downloaded images then will be converted to image format in Tiff and the pre-processing procedure.

3.4. Data processing

3.4.1. Image Pre-Processing

Pre-processing aims to correct distorted data in order to create more faithful representation of the original scene, this typically involves the initial processing of raw image data to correct for geometric distortions, to calibrate the data radiometrically, and to eliminate noise present in the data. Moreover, during the image pre-processing the Layer staking, subset and resolution merge was done with consideration the property in Landsat 8.

Layer stacking to build a new multiband file from Geo-referenced images of various pixel sizes, extents, and projections. The input bands had been re-sampled and re-projected to a common user-selected output projection and pixel size. The output file usually has a geographic extent that either encompasses all of the input file extents or only the data extent where all of the files overlap. Accordingly, six bands of the Landsat 7 images (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7) of each year and 6 bands (1,2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7) for Landsat 8 were layer stacked to form one full image with all bands to help the interpreter understand all features in the study area. Layer stacking had been done for six bands

A subset through this tool analyst can get only part of satellite image which covers study area. In this case user can subset image for that part only for further digital image processing. Its mean, this process reduces time and efforts for digital image processing.

Resolution merge different data such as satellite imagery from the same sensor but with different resolution, satellite imagery from different sensors with varying resolution, satellite imagery with ancillary information can be merged to improve the visual and analytical quality of the data. In other words, is combining high-resolution image include panchromatic band of 15m with other bands which has 30m of resolution.

3.4.2. Image processing

1. Image classification

The overall objective of image classification was categorized all pixels of an image into land cover classes. Normally, multispectral data was used to perform the classification, and the spectral pattern present within the data for each pixel was used as numerical basis for categorization. In this study supervised classification was used where the operator determines the areas where a particular type of land cover was present and then the computer computes the spectral signatures. Totally, five LULC classes were established as Agriculture, building, forest, vegetation and swamp.

In the supervised classification technique, the maximum likely hood algorithm was classifying the image based on the training sites (signatures) provided by the user based on the field knowledge. The maximum likelihood classifier was one of the most popular methods of classification in remote sensing, in which a pixel with the maximum likelihood was classified into the corresponding classes. The method was used in this project because it had some advantages in that: The classifier quantitatively evaluates both the variance and covariance of the category spectral response patterns when classifying an unknown pixel. This was done by assuming that the distribution of the cloud of points forming the category training data was normally distributed. The probability density functions were used to classify an unidentified pixel by computing the probability of the pixel value belonging to each class.

Three dated Landsat images (2000 - 2010 and 2020) were compared using supervised classification technique. After land use/cover classification system has been chosen, training sites were carefully selected in sufficient homogeneity to maximize the accuracy of classification in the image. In the supervised classification technique, three images with different dates were independently classified. This step was probably the most important part of supervised classification, for it's the spectral signatures extracted from these sites that was determine the overall classification accuracy, and thus the utility of the final thematic map. Accurate classifications were imperative to insure precise change-detection results.

2. Accuracy assessment

Accuracy assessment or validation was a critical step in the handling of remote sensing data. The overall accuracy of the classified image compares how each of the pixels is arranged versus the actual land conditions acquired from their corresponding ground truth information. Ground truth points were collected using a Google earth and handheld GPS which were used to assess the accuracy of classified image. These points were later used to assess the accuracy of the classified images.

3. Change detection

Three dated Landsat images (2000 - 2010 and 2020) have been compared using supervised classification technique. After land use/cover classification system has been chosen, training sites were carefully selected in sufficient homogeneity to maximize the accuracy of classification in the image. In the supervised classification technique, three images with different dates are independently classified. Those classified imageries have been taken as input for change detection process by using matrix union; this have been provided retrospective analysis of landscape cover change. As result, this have been used to analyse Landscape cover of Nyabugogo wetland.

3.4.5. Flowchart of the study

Table 3.2: Methodology flowchart

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

In this chapter, we discussed about results from land use/land cover (LULC) changes of Nyabugogo wetland from 2000-2010-2020. Rwanda. The study considered LULC changes that happened in 20 years from 2000 to 2020. With the help of Remote Sensing and GIS software, Land use/Land cover (LULC) changes were detected. Multi-temporal remote sensing images (Landsat imagery) were used to generate land use/land cover (LULC) maps. Two satellite images were collected, preprocessed, and classified through supervised Image classification stages in ERDAS. Then corresponding maps were exported by ArcGIS 10.7. where some important classes including water bodies, wetlands, agriculture, vegetation, forest, and built-up area were classified and detected for changes using both Image change workflow.

Post classification image differencing was used to show the landscape cover in in Nyabugogo wetland. The classified study area was mapped, quantified, analyzed and evaluated.

The classified images had five land cover classes such as Agriculture, building, forest, vegetation and swamp, which were presented in differently. Surfaces with similar spectral properties presented a challenge in the classification process leading to misclassification of some land covers.

4.2. Land Use/Cover Map of Nyabugogo Wetland In 2000

Figure 4.2 below describe the different land cover types existing in Study area in 2000. The classes type was identified during image classification are five, where yellow color represents the area covered by forest, red color represents the vegetation in the study area, sienna color represent wetland, blue color present area covered by agriculture and dark blue color represent build-up area.

Figure 4.2: Land scape cover of Nyabugogo wetland in 2000

Table 4.3 shows five classes include vegetation, built up, forest, wetland and agriculture classes. In 2000 agriculture class was dominated in Nyabugogo wetland. This land use land cover map 2000 in Nyabugogo wetland. Indicates that agriculture class covered 44.52%, building class covered 21.60%, vegetation class covered 19.74 %, forest class cover 5.67 and wetland class covered 8.41% of the total area.

NO	CLASS	Area	Percentage
1	Wetland zone	3654445.7	8.41
2	Building	13025124	21.60
3	Forest	1641097	5.67
4	Vegetation	6491022.8	19.74
5	Agriculture	7678348.9	44.52

Table 4.2: Classes and percentage of 2000

4.3. LAND COVER MAP OF NYABUGOGO WETLAND IN 2010

Figure 4.3 below describe the different land cover types existing in Study area in 2010. The classes type was identified during image classification are five, where yellow color represents the area covered by vegetation, green color represents the agriculture in the study area, sienna color represent wetland, blue color present area covered by forest and yellow color represent build-up area.

Figure 4.3: Landscape cover of Nyabugogo wetland in 2010

Table 4.4 shows five classes include vegetation, built up, forest, wetland and agriculture classes. In 2010 building class was dominated in Nyabugogo wetland. This land use land cover map 2010 in Nyabugogo wetland. Indicates that building class covered 39.1%, forest cover 6.64%, agriculture class covered 24.61%, vegetation class covered 18.73% and wetland class covered 9.43% of the total area.

NO	CLASS	Area	Percentage
1	Wetland zone	374445.7	9.43
2	Agriculture	29925124	24.61
3	Forest	1841097	6.64
4	Vegetation	6771022.8	18.73
5	Building	788348.9	39.1

Table 4.3: Classes and percentage of 2010

4.4. LAND COVER MAP OF NYABUGOGO WETLAND IN 2020

Figure 4.4 below describe the different land cover types existing in Study area in 2020. The classes type was identified during image classification are five, where yellow color represents the area covered by wetland, dark blue color represents the agriculture in the study area, red color represents vegetation, blue color present area covered by build-up area and light-yellow color represent forest.

Figure 4.4.: Landscape cover of Nyabugogo wetland in 2020

Table 4.5 revealed five classes include vegetation, built up, forest, wetland and agriculture classes. In 2020 building class was dominated in Nyabugogo wetland. This land use land cover map 2020 in Nyabugogo wetland. Indicates that building class covered 68.1%, agriculture class covered 19.60%, forest class cover 2.10%, vegetation class covered 3.72% and wetland class covered 6.48% of the total area.

NO	CLASS	Area	Percentage
1	Wetland zone	374445.7	6.48
2	Agriculture	29925124	19.60
3	Forest	1841097	2.10
4	Vegetation	6771022.8	3.72
5	Building	788348.9	68.1

Table 4.4: Classes and percentage of 2020

4.5. CHANGE DETECTION MAP OF NYABUGOGO WETLAND BETWEEN 2000 - 2010 - 2020

Figure 4.5 below describe the different land cover types existing in change detection map of Nyabugogo wetland from 2000 – 2010 to 2020. The classes type was identified during image classification are five, where dark green color represents the area covered by agriculture - forest, grey color represents the building – agriculture in the study area, light green color represents forest - wetland area, red color present area covered by vegetation – vegetation area and sienna color represent wetland zone – building.

**Figure 4.5: Change detection map of Nyabugogo wetland between
2000 - 2010 – 2020**

This result showed that or indicates that built up area increased from 21.67% to 68.1% in 2000 and 2020 The **figure 4.5** shows change detection map from 2000 to 2010 to 2020 in Nyabugogo wetland indicates that built up class covered 21.6%, 39.1% and 68.1% respectively and

Agriculture class covered 44.52% in 2000 and 19.60% in 2020 therefore the built-up area has been increased and Agriculture also decreased from 2000 to 2020.

Change	Area	Percentage
Wetland zone – Building	1662445.1	5.74
Agriculture – forest	7148448.7	24.68
Forest – Wetland	1641097	5.67
Vegetation - vegetation	6491022.8	22.41
Agriculture - Building	12026012	41.50

Table 4.5: Classes of change detection from 2000 to 2010 to 2020

CHAPTER 5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

The land use and land cover changes in Nyabugogo wetland from 2000 to 2010 to 2020 indicate a complex transformation. Over this period, rapid urbanization and infrastructure development have led to a substantial reduction in natural vegetation and wetland area. Agricultural expansion into the wetland and land reclamation for development purposes have contributed to wetland degradation and habitat loss. These changes have likely had adverse effects on the wetland's biodiversity, water quality, and hydrological characteristics, potentially increasing the risk of flooding. While conservation efforts and climate change influences may play a role in mitigating these impacts, comprehensive monitoring and conservation strategies are needed to safeguard Nyabugogo wetland's ecological integrity and ensure sustainable land use practices.

5.2. Recommendations

The government must implement comprehensive land-use planning and zoning regulations to control urban expansion and infrastructure development, prioritizing the preservation of wetland ecosystems.

Promoting sustainable agricultural practices that minimize encroachment into the wetland area and prevent further habitat degradation.

Investing in wetland restoration and reforestation projects to enhance biodiversity and improve water quality.

Strengthening monitoring and assessment efforts to track changes and enforce environmental regulations.

Enhancing public awareness and community engagement to support conservation efforts and sustainable land use practices in the wetland.

It's better to collaborate with local and international stakeholders to address climate change impacts and ensure the long-term resilience of Nyabugogo wetland.

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Appendix

